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ORGANIZATION OF ISLAMIC BANK ACTIVITY

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Abstract:

examines empirical studies with a focus on Islamic finance literature and identifies areas for future study. The previous literature on Islamic finance was based on the theoretically created Islamic economic principles of social justice and fairness, which were developed from the main texts of Sharia in conjunction with some analytical frameworks. The focus of subsequent research has been on empirical studies rather than comprehensive analytical and theoretical postulations. Despite the large number of empirical research on Islamic banking, there is a growing corpus of empirical literature on Islamic finance that focuses on corporate finance. The available literature paints a contrasting picture of Islamic financial tools and marketplaces.

Keywords: Islamic finance, Islamic capital market, takaful, murobaha, mushoraka, muzoraba,

1. Introduction

Conventional financial studies evolved into a separate subset discipline of economics in the 1950s (Fama 2011). Islamic economics, on the other hand, is a subtopic, and in the earliest stages of its growth, the birth of Islamic finance is concurrently explored within the context of Islamic economics (Hassan and Aldayel, 1998). Due to the failure of socioeconomic justice, which still takes advantage of the poor in society, Islamic economics and finance studies were born. For instance, when the borrower lacks the funds to launch a small business, it is ironically sensible to demand additional fees as usury in this situation. As acknowledged in the early corporate finance studies (Modigliani and Miller 1958).

The Islamic financial method of transaction is less prone to the complicated market crises that are tied to debt settlement. For instance, minimal leverage and increased real asset investments are two characteristics of Islamic equities portfolios (Ashraf et al. 2017). As a result, Islamic finance's asset. Aims to accomplish optimal resource allocation for more meaningful societal wellbeing enhancement, then this may be the case.

2.1 Islamic Finance The epistemology of Islamic finance and economics go back to Sharia (Islamic law) principles which are deduced from the guidance of the Quran (the sacred book of Islam), *Sunnah* (the tradition of the Prophet), the scholars' consensus (*Ijma*), analogy (*Qiyas*), and exertion (*Ijtihad*) (Pervez 1990; Maghrebi, Mirakhor, and Iqbal 2016)². The primary transactional modalities used to build

Islamic finance paradigm is on the promotion of social well-being that is associated to the risk-sharing perspective than risk-shifting or transfer. The system therefore is aimed towards efficient risk allocation to influence the participation of all economic agents on the participation in real economic activities. Despite the fact that contemporary Islamic finance system was developed on the platform of the modern finance, the former has other restrictions that make the system differ from the latter (Maghrebi, Mirakhor, and Iqbal 2016). Moreover, establishing truthfulness among the contract parties is an intrinsic to risks and rewards system. Thus, the functional pillars that are expected to guide this frame are nested within the moral and justice system, which is also found in the earlier works of conventional philosophers. The work of Adam Smith on the moral sentiment is one of that literature that shares common perspectives with Islamic financial economics towards establishing social justice.

The latest Islamic finance FinTech is one of the most high-quality industries in the industry and still produces many products. The general practices of Islamic finance and banking emerged with the establishment of Islam. For this, institutional Islamic finance was established after the 20th century. According to the Qardus publication, at the moment, the income of the Islamic sector is growing from 15% to 25% per fiscal year, and Islamic financial institutions are managing more than 2.7 trillion dollars in assets worldwide.

Currently, the three countries with the best implementation of Islamic finance, Saudi Arabia, Iran, and Malaysia, own 66 percent of the global market. According to the organization "Islamic banking and finance" in Uzbekistan (AlHuda), the growth of the Islamic finance industry in the CIS countries is slower than in other countries, but due to the growing opportunities in this region, it is attracting the attention of the international banking industry. If the governments of the CIS countries take the initiative to develop this sector, the work of Islamic banking will grow significantly in the next five years. Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan and Uzbekistan are likely to be key players leading this expansion of Islamic banking and finance in the CIS. Today, interest in Islamic finance is growing in Uzbekistan. Uzbekistan is an important country of Central Asia with more than 35 million inhabitants, 93 percent of its population are Muslims. It is not only rich in gas, oil and other natural resources, but it has been one of the centers of science and Islam since time immemorial. Initially, in 2003 and 2004, Uzbekistan took important steps towards the recognition of Islamic finance through its membership in IDB and the Islamic Corporation for the Development of the Private Sector (ICD). The stable relationship between these institutions and the government has allowed Islamic finance to gain an entry point into this market

2.2 The Principles of the Islamic Capital Market

The general principles of Islamic finance are consistent with the other guidelines of Islamic law, which prohibits activities related to social life (immorality, alcohol, fraud, corruption, gambling, pork, speculations, and pornography among others), and economic gain (interest, gambling, speculation, fraud, and corruption etc.). In the particular context of Islamic finance, Hussain, Shahmoradi, and Turk (2015) enumerated three major principles (equity, participation, and ownership) that guide the ideal Islamic financial transactions. First, the emphasis is on the equity principle that eliminates the unproductive accumulation of wealth through interest and excessive risk-taking by the entrepreneur that might end in squandering the entire business capital in seeking for higher returns, and on wealth distribution, which is basically *zakat* and other forms of charity. Therefore, supporting one another will eliminate the vast disparity between rich and poor, and the parties involved in a particular contract have a duty to disclose truthful information between them. Second, participation is in line with reward and risk sharing contracts that are opposed to interest-based financing and promote direct investment in the productive sectors of the economy. The third principle denounces disposing of property that is not owned by the seller such as short selling. Therefore, the rights of ownership prevail in this situation and stands as the foundation for linking financial transactions with a real sector of the economy. The first generation of theorists on Islamic economics and finance emphasized participating contracts based on profit and loss sharing, which mostly take the form of *Mudarabah* and *Musharaka* contracts. However, more recent developments in the system have shifted towards lease and sale-based contracts, while fee-based contracts stand as an auxiliary to some financial products (*Mudarabah* and *Murabaha*) (Hussain, Shahmoradi, and Turk 2015).

2.3 Islamic insurance

Contemporary business and other aspects of life are indemnified with an insurance cover to mitigate the catastrophes that arise from risks and losses attached to lives, property, and commercial activities. Like every segment of life, financial institutions are mandated to have insurance cover against unwanted calamity. As Sharia scholars prohibited conventional insurance at a time when the demand for insurance was increasing among Islamic financial institutions, Islamic insurance (*Takaful*) emerged in the late 1970s (Ayub 2007). The prohibition of conventional insurance is because of the risk transfer to another party, and the inclusion of *Riba* (interest), uncertainty and gambling therein. *Takaful* is considered to be the Shariabased alternative to conventional insurance through the reciprocated guarantee of repayment in a cooperative manner which takes place in the event of loss (Siddiqi

2006). As a matter of principle, *Takaful* is regarded as mutual assistance derived from the *Kafala* (guarantee), which provides mutual solidarity and risk-sharing between or among the group members (World Bank and Islamic Development Bank Group 2017). The idea of conventional insurance is transformed into an arrangement of contributing donations (*Tabarru*) to cover the losses of the members through mutual assistance. The members sacrifice to share the responsibility through payment of a subscription by each participating policyholder. That is, the cooperators in this arrangement agree to share the losses of their co-member in need of help based on a risk-sharing formula. However, the Islamic Financial Services Board (2009) highlight from experience that the mutual form of conventional insurance companies has problems implementing effective governance as their size increases above a certain threshold. Nevertheless, empirical studies are inadequate for verifying the position of real mutual *Takaful* entities. As a result of particular difficulties in their operations, most *Takaful* arrangements are based on a hybrid structure. Hayat and Malik (2014) highlighted that most of the countries offering *Takaful* are not complying with mutuality contracts but instead prefer the formation of an entity through sharing capital. They highlighted this issue as a result of the difficulty of the entity in meeting the required regulatory capital through mutual cooperative donations, which leads the corporation to take on hybrid mutuality form²². As such, Ayub (2007) identified other difficulties relating to the *Takaful* industry, including the capital requirements, having the operational efficiency to compete favorably in the market, the legal framework, capacity development, and the perceptions of the public about insurance

However, Khan (2015) suggested that *Takaful* corporations should give incentives to their contributors based on surplus-sharing (i.e., based on a *Mudarabah* contract) in all *Takaful* contracts, since they are considered to be cooperative ventures. In this scenario, the author neglected the fact that other contracts such as *wadiah* and *wakalah* have different effects on the level of acceptance, information asymmetry, risk coverage, and efficiency. Nonetheless, Ayub (2007) argued that *Takaful* cannot be feasible under the *Mudaraba* and *Mudarabah–Wakala* hybrid model, although the relationship is the best practice under a *Tabarru* arrangement. Islamic insurance has wide ranging acceptance in Malaysia and other countries practicing Islamic finance. For instance, in Bangladesh, *Takaful* has experienced enough successful growth to require a separate regulatory authority from the government to strengthen its activities (Khan et al. 2016).

Table 3 summarizes the significant findings on *Takaful* transactions. An empirical investigation on *Takaful* in Malaysia reveals that demand for the *Takaful* products positively depends on individual income, education, development of Islamic

banks, and the proportion of the Muslim population (Sheriff and Shaairi 2013). However, another investigation did not find sufficient evidence that strict Sharia compliance measures reduce underpricing of insurance offers (Boulanouar and Alqahtani 2016). Therefore, it is clear that even highly regulated industries are not free from the effect of information asymmetry, which mostly plays a role in the initial public offer of Islamic insurance. Operationally, cost efficiency in the *Takaful* industry is an essential ingredient that will lead to self-sufficiency. Thus the size of the board and firm coupled with product specialization has been found to influence cost efficiency, but splitting the top management does not have any effect. Therefore, the need to understand the economic efficiency of the *Takaful* industry goes beyond evaluating the costs, since the expectation is for the industry to compete favorably in terms of quality coverage, timely delivery, price, and avoiding malpractice. This is a growth area of empirical research, as more and more data will help us answer other important questions about the insurance industry as it relates to the *Takaful* industry (Hala, Adams, and Hardwick 2010). Similarly, Hala et al. (2014) reaffirmed the influence of board size and composition on cost efficiency in the *Takaful* industry of 17 countries across the globe. There is a need for further empirical studies in the area of *Takaful* insurance, especially on ascertaining their performance, solvency, and benefit distribution. Since the origin and specification of *Takaful* contracts differ from those of conventional insurance, there is a need for an adequate methodology that will consider the situation where a contributor is not at risk for a long period.

Authors	Period	Sample and countries	Methodology	Main Findings
Hala Adams and Hardwick (2010)	2014-2016	26 Takaful non-life insurance companies	DEA and second-stage logit transformation Regression model	Significant effect on cost efficiency whereas board size
Sherif and Shaairi (2013)	1896-2010	Malaysia	Ordinary least squares	Income ,islamic banking development , level of education
Hala et al.(2014)	2004-2007	17 Islamic countries	DEA and logistic regression	The efficiency of developed

				non-life insurance
Boulamour and Alqahtani (2016)	2007-2013	33 insurance firms listed in Saudi Arabia	OLS regression	Saudia Arabi's insurance companies

Conclusion

In conclusion, it can be said that the field of Islamic financial services will be an important factor, foundation and development perspective for the bright future of Uzbekistan, as a result, the interest of foreign investors in the country that reflects the deep roots of Islam in its culture will increase, and the government will use this opportunity for the welfare of the people and it will be possible to achieve full use in the sustainable development of the country.

The principles promoted by Islamic finance aim to develop a sustainable society based on strong economic and ethical values.

References:

1. <https://www.gazeta.uz/oz/2022/10/17/islamic-finance/>
2. <https://www.bukhari.uz/?p=22678>
3. <https://www.isdb.org/uzbekistan>
4. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Islamic_banking_and_finance
5. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/333698447_A_Contemporary_Review_of_Islamic_Finance_and_Accounting_Literature